

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			μ_{eff} B.M.
		Mo	Metal	N	
$\text{Cu}_2[\text{Mo}(\text{ON})_4(\text{OH})_4]$	Violet	24.02	31.95	14.01	2.0
		(24.30)	(32.15)	(14.17)	
$\text{Ag}_4[\text{Mo}(\text{ON})_4(\text{OH})_4]$	Brown	13.64	62.20	7.40	Dia.
		(13.71)	(61.71)	(8.00)	
$\text{Ni}_2[\text{Mo}(\text{ON})_4(\text{OH})_4]$	Pale green	24.60	29.84	7.00	3.3
		(24.91)	(30.46)	(7.26)	
$\text{Co}_2[\text{Mo}(\text{ON})_4(\text{OH})_4]$	Chocolate brown	24.56	29.99	7.02	4.8
		(24.89)	(30.53)	(7.26)	
$(\text{UO}_2)_2[\text{Mo}(\text{ON})_4(\text{OH})_4]$	Brown	11.36	58.20	6.40	Dia.
		(11.88)	(58.90)	(6.90)	

central metal ion of these octacoordinated complexes, where d -orbital splits into four levels⁶, $B_1(d_{x^2-y^2}) < A_1(d_{z^2}) < E(d_{xz}, d_{yz}) < B_2(d_{xy})$. The spectra closely resembled those obtained for similar systems⁷.

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Coordination Template Reactions. Part-V.
Complexes of Macrocyclic Ligand Dibenzo-
[c, j]-1,6,9,14-tetraazacyclohexadeca-
1,6,8,13-tetraene with Copper(II) and
Nickel(II) Ions

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A large number of transition metal complexes derived from macrocycles obtained by the self-condensation of three or four molecules of *o*-aminobenzaldehyde have been reported¹⁻⁴. In the

present communication, an attempt has been made to use *m*-aminobenzaldehyde, for which self-condensation is expected to be less favourable and hence, the aldehyde has been initially condensed with ethylenediamine and finally with glyoxal to result in a closed ring tetradentate N_4 donor (L) which forms planar complexes with Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} .

Experimental

The complexes were prepared in three steps.

***N,N'*-Bis(3-nitrophenyl)ethylenediamine (1)**: To a solution of ethylenediamine (0.01 mol, 0.60 ml) in methanol was added *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde (0.02 mol, 3.0 ml) slowly with constant stirring and the mixture was refluxed for 3 h. The resulting yellow crystals were filtered, washed with methanol, dried and analysed (Table 1).

***N,N'*-Bis(3-aminophenyl)ethylenediamine (2)**: 1 was reduced with Sn/HCl solution and the resulting product (2) precipitated out as amine hydrochloride, was washed with water, methanol and used as such.

Preparation of complexes: Compound 2 (0.01 mol, 0.27 g) in methanol was mixed with appropriate metal(II) salt (0.01 mol). pH of the solution was adjusted to 6-7 and refluxed for 8 h. A solution of glyoxal (0.01 mol, 0.58 ml) in methanol was then added to it and the solution was further refluxed for 10 h. The reaction mixture was purified by running over tlc plates and the complexes were crystallised out using petroleum ether-acetone mixture and analysed (Table 1).

Preparation of free macrocycle (L): The free macrocycle was obtained by extricating out nickel from the nickel(II) chloride complex by the following method. Nickel(II) chloride complex (0.01 mol) in methanol was refluxed for 2 h with potassium cyanide (0.04 mol) in water. The resulting precipitate of $[\text{Ni}(\text{CN})_4]^{2-}$ was filtered over a silica column; the resulting solution was run over tlc plates and the free macrocycle crystallised out by using petroleum ether and characterised (Table 1).

Results and Discussion

Elemental analysis and molar conductance data reveal the molecular formulae of the complexes as $[\text{M}(\text{L})\text{X}_2]$, where $\text{M} = \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}$ and Ni^{II} ; $\text{X} = \text{Cl}^-$, SCN^- , ClO_4^- , BF_4^- ; $\text{L} = \text{dibenzo}[c, j]-1,6,9,14\text{-tetraazacyclohexadeca-1,6,8,13-tetraene}$ ($\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_4$). The complexes dissolve in methanol to give conducting solutions thus suggesting that the anions are not coordinated.

The molecular formulae of the three products 1, 2 and L has been assigned on the basis of their elemental analysis data (Table 1). In their ir spectra, strong absorptions are observed in the range 2900-2700 and 1600-1450 cm^{-1} which correspond to CH and aromatic ring vibrations. In the spectra of

NOTES

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Compd.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				Λ_M^* $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	μ_{eff}^{**} B.M.
	M	O	H	N		
$C_{10}H_{14}N_4O_4$ (1)	—	58.42 (58.89)	4.82 (4.29)	17.56 (17.17)	—	—
$C_{10}H_{10}N_4Cl$ (2)	—	62.81 (61.84)	7.10 (6.13)	19.61 (18.04)	—	—
$C_{10}H_{10}N_4$ (L)	—	75.18 (75.52)	4.56 (4.89)	19.92 (19.58)	—	—
$[Cu(C_{10}H_{10}N_4)]Cl_2$	14.72 (15.03)	51.20 (51.55)	3.68 (3.34)	13.72 (13.36)	175	2.11
$[Cu(C_{10}H_{10}N_4)](SON)_2$	12.92 (13.54)	51.01 (51.61)	2.85 (3.01)	18.55 (18.06)	195	2.19
$[Cu(C_{10}H_{10}N_4)](ClO_4)_2$	10.32 (11.49)	39.32 (39.41)	2.95 (2.55)	10.75 (10.21)	216	2.22
$[Cu(C_{10}H_{10}N_4)](BF_4)_2$	11.75 (12.04)	41.80 (41.30)	2.18 (2.67)	10.25 (10.70)	222	2.21
$[Ni(C_{10}H_{10}N_4)]Cl_2$	12.80 (13.55)	52.68 (52.30)	3.71 (3.38)	12.81 (12.55)	196	0.99
$[Ni(C_{10}H_{10}N_4)](SON)_2$	11.70 (12.22)	53.85 (53.27)	3.62 (3.05)	17.89 (18.94)	201	0.92
$[Ni(C_{10}H_{10}N_4)](ClO_4)_2$	9.85 (10.85)	39.54 (39.92)	2.12 (2.58)	9.70 (10.35)	220	1.01
$[Ni(C_{10}H_{10}N_4)](BF_4)_2$	10.48 (10.85)	41.41 (41.86)	2.50 (2.71)	10.21 (10.85)	218	0.89

*In MeOH. **At 300 K.

1, two strong bands due to ν_{asym} and ν_{sym} nitro groups are seen at 1525 and 1440 cm^{-1} . These disappear from the spectra of 2 and L and one additional strong band appears at 3320 cm^{-1} in the former corresponding to amino and in the latter at 1660 cm^{-1} corresponding to azomethine stretch.

The ^1H nmr spectra of compound 1 contain signals at δ 7.28 (s), 7.5–7.85 (q), 8.0–8.2 (d) and 8.4–8.5 (d) corresponding to the four protons of the phenyl group and two singlets at δ 2.0 and 3.9 for CH_3 and CH protons. The spectrum of compound 2 is similar with an additional singlet at δ 5.8 corresponding to the protons of amino group. In the spectra of compound L the latter singlet due to NH_2 protons disappears indicating that condensation with the consequent formation of Schiff base has occurred, while the other signals appear at almost the same position. On the basis of these data the following structure is suggested for the macrocycle which behaves as tetradentate ligand (L).

In the ir spectra of the complexes the bands at 2900–2700 (CH) and 1590–1450 cm^{-1} (aromatic ring) remain almost unshifted as expected⁵⁻⁸. The azomethine stretch shows a significant negative shift and is observed at $1600 \pm 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, indicating coordination from the nitrogen atom⁹⁻¹¹ of L. The

bands corresponding to different anions are observed in their usual ionic ranges, thus supporting the conductance data.

The magnetic moments of the Cu^{II} complexes lie in the usual range of one unpaired electron, while for the Ni^{II} complexes the values lie in the range 0.88–1.00 B.M. indicating their partially paramagnetic nature which is due to the spin cross over between the diamagnetic singlet and paramagnetic triplet states of the ion.

The reflectance spectra of the Cu^{II} complexes show a single broad band centered around 16.00 kK assigned to $^2B_{1g} \rightarrow ^2A_{1g}$ transition. Two weak shoulder are also observed on either sides of the main band and are assigned to as $^2B_{1g} \rightarrow ^2E_g$ (22.00 kK) and $^2B_{1g} \rightarrow ^2B_{2g}$ (12.50 kK) transitions respectively, of planar geometry¹²⁻¹⁴. In case of the Ni^{II} complex the main band is seen at 18.50 kK which is assigned to $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1A_{2g}$ transition. A few weak bands are observed at 10.00–12.50 and 22.00–25.00 kK, which correspond to planar geometries for the above complexes¹⁵⁻¹⁷.

The Dq values are found to be very high ($\sim 1600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for the Cu^{II} complexes and $\sim 1150 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for the Ni^{II} complexes) suggesting that the macrocycle used is a sufficiently strong ligand. In accordance with this the inter-electronic repulsion parameter B' and nepheluxetic ratio (β) for the complexes also correspond to the presence of sufficient degree of covalency on the metal-ligand bond. It is also observed that the values of these parameters are consistent and remain independent of anions which is expected as the latter are not coordinated.

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Complexes of some Bivalent Metal Ions with
4-Salicylaldimino-3-mercapto-5-phenyl-
1,2,4-triazole

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WE report the preparation and characterisation of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes with 4-salicylaldimino-3-mercapto-5-phenyl-1,2,4-triazole (SMPTH_2)^{1,2}.

Experimental

Preparation of complexes : An aqueous ethanolic solution of metal(II) halide (0.005 mol in 50 ml) and an ethanolic solution of the ligand (0.01 mol in 100 ml) were mixed. The pH of the mixture was adjusted to 7–8 by adding concentrated ammonia and refluxed for 0.5 h. The Cu^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes separated immediately but the Ni^{II} , Co^{II} and Zn^{II}

complexes separated on adding an equal volume of water. The complexes were filtered, washed with aqueous ethanol and dried (90–100°).

The complexes were characterised on the basis of their elemental analyses, room temperature (304°), magnetic moment (μ_{eff}), uv and ir spectral data.

Results and Discussion

Elemental analyses (Table 1) correspond to 1 : 1 metal-ligand stoichiometry for all the complexes.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Analysis % :		Mol. wt. Found/(Calcd.)	μ_{eff} B.M.
	Found	(Calcd.)		
[Ni(SMPT)(H ₂ O) ₂]	M	N	755 (777)	2.67
	14.98 (15.10)	14.89 (14.40)		
[Co(SMPT)(H ₂ O) ₂]	M	N	758 (778)	4.92
	15.32 (15.15)	14.28 (14.89)		
Cu(SMPT)	M	N	682 (715)	1.62
	17.94 (17.76)	15.73 (15.65)		
Zn(SMPT)	M	N	698 (719)	Dia.
	18.31 (18.18)	15.31 (15.57)		
Cd(SMPT)	M	N	793 (813)	Dia.
	27.71 (27.64)	13.81 (13.77)		

The complexes were found to be slightly soluble in DMF, dioxane, ethanol and acetone but insoluble in benzene and chloroform. Insolubility of the complexes restricted accurate determination of their molecular weight ; though approximate values (Rast method in camphor) correspond to dimeric formula of the complexes. The solutions of the complexes are almost non-conducting indicating their non-ionic nature.

The room temperature μ_{eff} values of 4.92 B.M. for [Co(SMPT)(H₂O)₂] and 2.67 B.M. for [Ni(SMPT)(H₂O)₂] indicate spin-free octahedral nature of the metal ions. A slightly lower μ_{eff} of the Ni^{II} complex (2.98 B.M. expected for a spin-free octahedral geometry) can be attributed to the dimeric species. A subnormal μ_{eff} value of 1.62 B.M. for Cu(SMPT) suggests copper–copper bonding or superexchange interaction through bridging oxygen atom in the complex molecules^{3,4}.

The medium band at 19 240 cm^{-1} and a shoulder near 22 730 cm^{-1} in the reflectance spectra of [Co(SMPT)(H₂O)₂] were assigned to ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ transition and spin-orbit coupling in ${}^4T_{1g}(P)$ state respectively^{5,7} in the octahedral field. The medium broad band at 16 130 cm^{-1} and a weak band at 17 240 cm^{-1} in the reflectance spectra of [Ni(SMPT)(H₂O)₂] were attributable to splitted ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ transition in a distorted octahedral field ; 23 250 cm^{-1} was due to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transition⁸⁻¹⁰ in the octahedral field. In solution, the complex displayed these transitions as medium and broad bands at 16 350 ($\epsilon_{\text{max}}=22$) and 23 450 cm^{-1} ($\epsilon_{\text{max}}=46$) respectively. A broad asymmetric band at 12 500–15 040 cm^{-1} and a strong band around